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ANALYSIS OF CURRENT TRENDS AND PRACTICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING ACCOUNTING

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Abstract: This article analyzes the current trends and practical opportunities for improving accounting in the agricultural sector. In particular, the issues of digitizing the accounting system, optimizing accounting policies, training qualified personnel, accurately calculating the cost of products, and increasing the financial discipline of economic entities through strengthening internal control are highlighted. The article contains recommendations for establishing effective and transparent accounting in the agricultural sector.

Keyword: agriculture, accounting, digitization, accounting policy, costing, internal control, audit, financial control, automated accounting, agricultural reporting.

A number of legislative and regulatory documents, well-thought-out programs have been adopted and are being consistently implemented to organize and further liberalize our economy on a completely new basis, improve its legal framework, and modernize and diversify production. In particular, the role of farms in the development and stabilization of our country's economy and their share in the gross domestic product are increasing year by year. Therefore, in order to further develop the activities of farms, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5199 was issued on 09.10.2017.

In this regard, the need to create favorable conditions for the promotion and development of diversified farms, which, in addition to the production of agricultural products, are engaged in processing, preparation, storage, sale, construction work and provision of services, was recognized as one of the priorities. In this regard, in order to ensure the implementation of the above decree, the issue of organizing diversified farms in our republic was raised. In order to positively resolve this issue, it is important not only to change their organizational structure, but also to effectively use and control the existing property in them. This control is carried out through the accounting system. In this case, the development of farms largely depends on state support, the level of service provided by credit and other financial organizations, and the correct establishment of the accounting system in farms. Therefore, today it is important to solve the existing problems in the accounting system of farms and its improvement.

The rapid development of today's economy requires that the form of accounting for a diversified farm should correspond to its content, information support for managing all processes of activity. The development of accounting in farms is not progressive in some places, but rather slow, evolutionary-delayed, since insufficient attention is paid to these problems in scientific and educational literature. This

determines the need to study the process of development of accounting and the methodological rules for its improvement in farms.

Some forms of accounting (memorial order, book order, simplified, etc.) are no longer consistent with the rapidly changing content and are becoming an obstacle not only to further development, but also to the effective functioning of this system as a management function. Therefore, the selection of convenient and effective forms of accounting is one of the most important tasks in the development of accounting.

In particular, in the organization of accounting in diversified farms, insufficient assessment of the practical importance of the form of accounting in the selection of accounting policies leads to disruptions in the information system and impedes the solution of the tasks set for accounting. As a result, this form of accounting leads to the continuation of inefficient work.

Therefore, the methodological and organizational improvement of accounting should be based on an analysis of specific needs for information. Meeting the growing information needs of internal and external users (especially investors, creditors, and tax authorities) requires the implementation of accounting functions and the tasks assigned to it (strategic goals). Only by developing and implementing all accounting functions, technologies, and mechanisms, can information be effectively used by internal and external users to solve the tasks assigned to accounting and achieve its goals.

Agriculture is one of the main sectors of the country's economy, and the effective conduct of financial and production processes in this area directly depends on the state of the accounting system. Improving accounting not only strengthens the financial discipline of business entities, but also rationally uses resources and increases competitiveness.

1. Digitalization and automation opportunities. Introduction of information technologies: The accuracy and speed of reporting increases through the use of electronic accounting programs (for example, 1C, AgroSoft, ERP systems). Cloud technologies: Allows you to access and manage data remotely, which is especially important for farms operating on large land areas.

2. Optimization of accounting policies. Taking into account the specific characteristics of agriculture: For example, introducing special accounting methods, taking into account factors such as the growing season, seasonality, and the movement of living assets (animals). Accurately reflect the movement of material resources: It is necessary to keep detailed records of resources such as seeds, fertilizers, fuels and lubricants.

3. Staff training. Update practical and theoretical knowledge of agricultural accountants by organizing regular training courses and seminars. Studying international experience: Introducing advanced accounting methodologies based on the recommendations of FAO and other organizations.

4. Integration with state reporting systems. Create the opportunity to submit reports of agricultural entities through online platforms. Tax reports, applications for subsidies and other financial documents should be maintained in a single system.

5. Improved approach to determining the cost of products. Keep separate records by type of activity: analyze costs in areas such as farming, livestock, poultry.

Cost calculation based on multi-factor analysis: Taking into account factors such as labor, equipment wear, and climatic conditions.

6. Strengthening the internal control and audit system. Introducing internal control mechanisms at each stage of production. Identifying and eliminating violations in advance through periodic financial analysis and audits.

Improving accounting in agriculture is carried out through modern digital technologies, qualified personnel, and approaches that comply with international standards. This creates the basis for the economic stability and development of economic entities.

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